

two principal sets for species, namely, matrix-derived $\dot{\text{C}}\text{H}_2\text{COCH}_3$ ($a_{\text{H}}=2.15$ mT; $g=2.0043$) and Pd^{III} paramagnetic centre at $g=2.184^9$. However, the photolysis of hexachloroiridate(IV) ions in acetate gave only the organic radical, $\dot{\text{C}}\text{H}_2\text{COCH}_3$ ($a_{\text{H}}=2.14$ mT) but no low-field absorption attributable¹⁰ to Ir^{II} as Ir^{III} is diamagnetic.

Thus, these preliminary studies support the formation of carbon-centred free radical intermediates by hydrogen atom abstraction mechanism (equations 1 and 2).

Acknowledgement

Sincere thanks are due to Prof. T. J. Kemp, Department of Chemistry, University of Warwick, Coventry, U.K., for the facilities and critically reviewing the present study and to Tata Institute of Fundamental Research, Bombay, for facilities to carry out some of the spin-trapping experiments. The financial assistance from the Royal Society of Chemistry, London, is gratefully acknowledged.

References

1. E. G. JANZEN, *Chem. Eng. News*, 1965, **43**, 50.
2. E. G. JANZEN and B. J. BLACKBURN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **91**, 4481.
3. E. G. JANZEN, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1971, **4**, 31; M. J. PERKINS, *Adv. Phys. Org. Chem.*, 1980, **17**, 1; A. G. FADNIS, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1988, **47**, 617.
4. G. V. NIZOVA, M. V. SERDOBOV, A. T. NIKITAEV and G. V. SHUL'FIN, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1984, **275**, 139; G. A. SHAGISULTANOVA, *Koord. Khim.*, 1981, **7**, 1527; R. E. CAMERON and A. B. BOCARSLY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1986, **25**, 2910.
5. A. G. FADNIS and T. J. KEMP, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1989, 1237.
6. A. G. FADNIS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1989, **66**, 273.
7. D. D. PERRIN, W. L. F. ARMSTRONG and D. D. PERRIN, "Purification of Laboratory Chemicals", Pergamon, New York, 1980.
8. D. REHOREK, C. M. DUBOSE and E. G. JANZEN, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1984, **83**, L7.
9. J. T. SUSS, A. RAIZMAN, S. SZAPIRO and W. LOW, *J. Magn. Reson.*, 1972, **6**, 438.
10. A. RAIZMAN, J. T. SUSS and W. LOW, *Phys. Revs. (B)*, 1977, **15**, 5184.

Synthesis of 5,6,7,8,2',4',5'-Heptamethoxy-flavone (Agecorynin-C)

S. C. SHAW*, A. S. JHA and (MRS.) ANJU K. GUPTA

Department of Chemistry, Patna University, Patna-800 005
 Manuscript received 3 August 1989, revised 15 February 1990,
 accepted 7 May 1990

QUIJANO and Calderone¹ isolated several new highly oxygenated flavonoids from *Ageratum corymbosum* Zucc. These are agecorynin-A (1) and agecorynin-B (2) and the flavones agecorynin-C (3) and agecorynin-D (4). But synthetic evidence has not been adduced so far in support of the structures assigned to these products. The present paper deals with the synthesis of agecorynin-C (3) by an unambiguous and simple route.

To embark upon the synthesis of 3, 1,2,3,5-tetramethoxybenzene was the starting material, which was prepared by following the method of Baker². On Friedel-Crafts acylation, 1,2,3,5-tetramethoxybenzene afforded 2-hydroxy-3,4,6-trimethoxyacetophenone (5), which on Elb's persulphate oxidation yielded 2,5-dihydroxy-3,4,6-trimethoxyacetophenone (6). Methylation of 6 with diazomethane gave 2-hydroxy-3,4,5,6-tetramethoxyacetophenone (7) which on treatment with 2,4,5-trimethoxybenzoyl chloride yielded the corresponding ester 2-(2',4',5'-trimethoxybenzoyloxy)-3,4,5,6-tetramethoxyacetophenone (8). The ester (8) on reaction with KOH in dry pyridine underwent Baker-Venkataraman rearrangement to produce 2-hydroxy-3,4,5,6-tetramethoxy-2',4',5'-trimethoxydibenzoylmethane (9) which on subsequent cyclisation with fused sodium acetate in glacial acetic acid medium afforded a product which was identical (m.m.p., ir, co-tlc) with the natural sample of agecorynin-C (3).

1; R=H
 2; R=OCH₃

3; R=CH₃
 4; R=H

5; R=R¹=R²=H (6); R=R¹=H, R²=OH
 7; R=R¹=H; R²=OCH₃
 8; R¹=H, R²=OCH₃, R=CO(C₆H₂)(2,4,5-trimethoxy)
 9; R=H, R²=OCH₃, R¹=CO(C₆H₂)(2,4,5-trimethoxy)

Experimental

All melting and boiling points are uncorrected. Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 237 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra were run at 100 MHz using TMS as internal standard.

2,5-Dihydroxy-3,4,6-trimethoxyacetophenone (6): To a stirred mixture of 2-hydroxy-3,4,6-trimethoxyacetophenone (11.2 g) and sodium hydroxide (20.0 g) in water (120 ml) was added during 4 h a solution of potassium persulphate (17.6 g) in water

(360 ml) and the stirring was continued for a further 2 h. After standing overnight the solution was acidified to congo red, filtered from a crystalline deposit and then extracted with benzene (100 ml). The solid and the concentrate of the benzene extract were the unchanged starting material (1.4 g). The aqueous layer was refluxed for 4 h with the addition of benzene (200 ml) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (100 ml). The benzene layer was separated, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and distilled off. The yellow crystalline mass obtained was crystallised from hot water to fine yellow needles (3.7 g, 33.3%), m.p. 115–17° (Found: C, 54.48; H, 5.91. $C_{11}H_{14}O_6$ requires: C, 54.54; H, 5.83%).

2-Hydroxy-3,4,5,6-tetramethoxyacetophenone (7): An ethereal solution of diazomethane generated from nitrosomethylurea (40.0 g) was dried over potassium hydroxide pellets. The methanolic solution of 2,5-dihydroxy-3,4,6-trimethoxyacetophenone (10.0 g) was added to the ethereal solution of diazomethane. The reaction mixture was kept overnight in a refrigerator. The excess diazomethane and the solvent were then removed from reaction mixture under reduced pressure. The crude liquid product was distilled at 115°/2 mm (8.5 g, 80%) (Found: C, 56.18; H, 6.32. $C_{12}H_{16}O_6$ requires: C, 56.24; H, 6.29%).

2-(2',4',5'-Trimethoxybenzoyloxy)-3,4,5,6-tetramethoxyacetophenone (8): 2,4,5-Trimethoxybenzoyl chloride (prepared from 2.3 g 2,4,5-trimethoxybenzoic acid) was added to a solution of 2-hydroxy-3,4,5,6-tetramethoxyacetophenone (2.0 g) in dry pyridine (15 ml) and heated at 100° for 1 h. The cooled reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice after the removal of pyridine under reduced pressure. The residue was washed with dilute hydrochloric acid. The ester (8) was crystallised from acetone-ethanol as colourless needles (3.0 g, 85%), m.p. 180–81° (Found: C, 58.58; H, 6.01. $C_{22}H_{26}O_{10}$ requires: C, 58.66; H, 5.82%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1728 (ester C=O) and 1670 cm^{-1} ($COCH_3$).

2-Hydroxy-3,4,5,6-tetramethoxy-2',4',5'-trimethoxydibenzoylmethane (9): Powdered potassium hydroxide (3.0 g) was added to a solution of the ester (8; 2.5 g) in dry pyridine (10 ml) and heated at 60° with stirring for 4 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and acidified. The resulting yellow diketone was filtered, washed, dried and crystallised from methanol as yellow needles (1.87 g, 75%), m.p. 129–30° (Found: C, 58.60; H, 5.91. $C_{22}H_{26}O_{10}$ requires: C, 58.66; H, 5.82%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3300–3600 (OH), 1617 (chelated β -diketone), 1570 and 1525 cm^{-1} (aromatic); positive $FeCl_3$ test.

5,6,7,8,2',4',5'-Heptamethoxyflavone (Agecorynin-C) (3): A mixture of 2-hydroxy-3,4,5,6-tetramethoxy-2',4',5'-trimethoxydibenzoylmethane (1.0 g), fused sodium acetate (1.8 g) and glacial acetic acid (15 ml) was refluxed for 4 h. Acetic acid was then removed under reduced pressure and water added to the cooled reaction mixture. The separated flavone was crystallised from acetone-pentane as colourless solid (0.76 g, 80%), m.p. 159–60° (lit.¹ 158–60°)

(Found: C, 59.89; H, 5.97. $C_{22}H_{24}O_9$ requires: C, 61.10; H, 5.59%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1640 (C=O), 1570 and 1520 cm^{-1} (aromatics); δ ($CDCl_3$) 3.95 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.97 (9H, s, $3 \times OCH_3$), 3.98 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.03 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.10 (3H, s, OCH_3), 6.57 (s, 3-H), 7.04 (s, 3'-H) and 7.54 (s, 6'-H).

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to express their sincere thanks to Prof. L. Quijano for providing the authentic sample of agecorynin-C.

References

1. L. QUIJANO, J. S. CALDERONE, F. GÓMEZG, I. E. SORIA and T. RIOS, *Phytochemistry*, 1980, **19**, 2439.
2. W. BAKER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 667

Studies on Vilsmeier-Haack Reaction. A New Route to 2-Chloroquinoline-3-carboxaldehydes and a Furoquinoline Derivative†

R. A. PAWAR*, P. B. BAJARE and S. B. MUNDADE

Department of Chemistry, S.S V.P. Sanstha's
Late Karmveer Dr. P. R. Ghogrey Science College,
Dhule-424 005

Manuscript received 5 October 1989, revised 30 March 1990,
accepted 11 May 1990

IN continuation of our interest in Vilsmeier-Haack reaction¹ and its synthetic applications, *para*-substituted-acetophenone oximes (**1a–d**) were converted into 2-chloroquinoline-3-carboxaldehydes (**2a–d**) in one step by Vilsmeier-Haack reagent (DMF/ $POCl_3$). We made use of this versatile intermediate **2** to build a linear furoquinoline derivative by a simple route (Scheme 1).

2-Chloroquinoline-3-carboxaldehyde is a versatile synthetic intermediate² because chlorine can be displaced by reactive nucleophiles and the aldehyde group is a suitable proximate reactive function for the construction of new heterocyclic ring. We report here a one-pot synthesis of compound **2**. Compounds **1a–d** were converted into **2a–d** using excess of $POCl_3$ (7 mol) and dimethylformamide (3 mol) by Vilsmeier-Haack reaction. Melting points and ir spectra of **2a–d** were found identical with those of the authentic samples prepared by the reported method².

The plausible mechanism for the reaction may involve Beckmann transformation of the oxime with aryl group migration to give acetanilides *in situ*

† Presented at the 9th International Congress of Heterocyclic Chemistry, Tokyo, Japan.